

Recommendation 1:

Artificial Intelligence & bots

Access to public sector information

Using *'artificial intelligence and bots'* to meet the business need *'Access to public sector information'*

Actual solutions and services:

In general it can be observed that artificial intelligence is one of the top emerging technologies in which a lot of research and development is happening right now.

However, the state of the art of artificial intelligence already permits to have several applications which could help to satisfy the need to access public sector information.

There are already many administrations, like Enfield Council, the Department of Homeland Security, North Carolina's Innovation Center, the Australian Tax Office or the government of Singapore which use artificial intelligence in the form of chatbots to interact with their citizens.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- **Overcoming the limitations of human nature (not limited by fatigue, boredom or emotions intercepting rational thinking).**
- **Undertaking laborious tasks – reducing human effort.**
- **Convenience – making daily life a lot easier with its several applications (auto-correct apps, personal assistants, gps, etc.)**
- **Saving the need of organisations for human resources.**
- **Carrying out repetitive and time-consuming tasks efficiently.**
- **Capable of carrying out dangerous or risky tasks.**

Opportunities

- **Personal Public Services Assistance.**
- **Intelligent Agents for Policy Decisions**
- **Automation in mainstream tasks**

Weaknesses

- Ethical and moral issues, found in embedding intelligence in a machine.
- Significant maintenance and repair costs to suit changing requirements.
- Lacking common sense, creativity, intuitiveness and the human touch.
- Difficulty in ensuring that AI will be used ethically.
- Not as efficient as humans in adapting responses, depending on changing situations.

Threats

- Hesitancy in fully delegating important tasks to AI applications.
- Fear of replacing humans in their job positions /unemployment.
- Fear of lateral thinking and multitasking abilities of humans gradually declining due to the reduced need to use their intelligence - humans becoming overly dependent on machines.
- Fear of destructive consequences if control of AI goes to the wrong hands.
- Fear of smart machines superseding and enslaving humans.

Access to public sector information:

Many individuals and organisations collect a broad range of different types of data in order to perform their tasks. The data provided by public sector is particularly significant both because of the quantity and quality, and centrality of the data it collects. However, there are certain barriers to opening up of data which include loss of control over the information, low information quality and privacy concerns for the public sector. Thus, it is least surprising that there still exists a reluctance in the public sector to collect and release relevant data. In view of these issues, few of the informants expressed the need to "Free access to cadastral and enterprises data" and that "Private companies depend on the PS will to open those data."

Artificial Intelligence and bots:

Technology field that draws upon computer science, mathematics, psychology, linguistics, philosophy, neuroscience and artificial psychology.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is intelligence exhibited by machines. In computer science, an "intelligent" machine is ideally a flexible rational agent that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chance of success at some goal. Colloquially, the term "artificial intelligence" is applied when a machine mimics cognitive functions such as "learning" and problem solving.

*From another point of view, artificial intelligence is the science of doing by computer the things that people can do and in contrast to normal hardware and software, enables a machine to perceive and respond to its changing environment.**

*Wikipedia Artificial intelligence. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artificial_intelligence. Accessed 14 June 2017.

World Economic Forum Top 10 emerging technologies of 2015. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2015/03/top-10-emerging-technologies-of-2015-2/#emergent-ai>. Accessed 14 June 2017.